

TRANSPORTATION STATUS IN PEDAGOGICAL PROCESS.

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Nowadays, using different interactive methods in higher education institutions, students pay great attention to the formation of independent thinking and independent thinking. Regardless of interactive methods, the relationship lies in its basis. The teacher always communicates with the students. Therefore, he must have perfectly mastered communal aspects and laws.

The main goals of the engagement partner are to find common ground, understand each other. The complexity of this process is that they can not find the same language or speak the same thoughts.

Interpretation of researchers' use of different means of interaction with the interlocutor, however, is also widely used in psychological manipulation. Different methods, techniques, tactics, techniques, strategies, etc. are used in the communication process. One of the main aspects of psychological manipulation in interaction and communication is the transformation.

The concept of transformation in the US in 1955 by E. Beech E. Byorn interpersonal relationships have led them to parents (conditional O), adult (conditionally K), and younger children (conditional B), depending on their characteristics. In the communication, each of these "I" states performs certain tasks and is necessary for this life. Taking into account the abovementioned, we conducted the TransStud Analy method of E. Byorn in the regional center of retraining and advanced training at the Ferghana State University. The results from respondents revealed how much intercultural relationships exist in the transational role of child, adult and parent.

Thus, the teacher uses the role of "Child" in relation to the student by 28 percent, "Big" role - 37 percent and "Parent" - 35 percent of respondents.

The results show that most respondents play the role of a "Big" person in interpersonal relationships, making decision-making through receiving and processing transmitted information, logical analysis of information, rational substantiation, and analysis-synthesis. These respondents are quick to gather information, gather information and make their own conclusions without delay. If uncertainty arises, they will think deeply about not giving up emotions in assessing this abstract. Such respondents are, in contrast to the situation of good

parental care, rather than adapting to normative and unilateral situations, but to the freedom of thought and freedom of choice, as well as understanding the situation in the future.

The subsequent outcome of the teacher's attitude towards the student is the role of "parent", and respondents who play the role "play" the role of father, sister, teacher, and head in interpersonal relationships. Also playing the role of "Parent"; In the case of "I am a good parent," he strives to give the student the opportunity to communicate, to give him different opportunities, to show kindness, to give full answers to all the questions, to help in various situations. To prevent some unwanted movements, she tries to correct the students. These respondents undertake any task (including assignments, even if they do not belong to them), with the student as with very close people. They repeat the words "We will do it together", "Do not be afraid," "We will help in everything". Additionally, reviewing, analyzing, and making short-term decision-making on the maternal well-being capacities allow for greater success. "I - critically squeezing parents" are emotionally depressed, harassed, criticized, and ordered if they are dissatisfied with the behaviors of their students.

The ultimate result of the transitional situation in the attitude toward the student is the role of the "Child", which is the role of the "natural baby" in the natural, impulsive, cunning, egocentric behavior, "flexible young boy" who needs help, feeling a sense of fear, contradictory behavior, the "rebellious child" is a manifestation of an act of self-denial, an act of self-denial.

It is based on the vital principles of emotions in "child" mode. At the same time, the behavior of a person is influenced by the child's true emotions. Childhood carries out special functions that are not part of the two states of the person above. It can give more power to cross-sections and dreams, which exhibit a sense of humor and effect as a result of the effects that make life pleasing, sometimes unpleasant. In addition, the childhood "I" can be independently resolved to find the strength needed to cope with the problem: difficulties that can not be solved or can not be confronted with another person's pressure, that is, the natural boy "I" (happiness , spontaneous reactions of nausea and other appearances), the flexible child "me" (flexible, guilty, guilty, and so on), the young boy who is the objector "me" (stupid, spit, laughter, etc.). In the case of a child, groom, public-loving artist, and young specialist will play "roles".

These are the norms of behavioral attitudes and, in all normative situations, contribute to individual action in the individual's life, as well as the

stereotypes that have been examined, to the realization of things that do not need the mind, and to take responsible responsibilities.

The attitudes of each person are proportionate to certain states of the mind. Another spiritual attitude depends on another behavioral set.

Therefore, in the context of interrelationship between teacher and student relations, taking into account the following points;

- The Uzbek language is so attractive, rich and beautiful that it is important to use all its capabilities in its own way and with skill;
- model the pedagogical behavior of the student to manage, which in turn allows the student to do the necessary action;
- strive to understand the ways in which others can deal with disagreements and how to get out of it;
- Everyone interacts with everyday life, but does not always succeed. Such dissatisfaction should not be taken at the disaster level;

Based on the above, we give teachers the following advice in pedagogical dialogue.

Do not be afraid of difficulties and failures;

- Do not escape the problem and try to solve it;
- The student who offers you an offer will definitely expect a positive answer. In that case, try to make the student's proposal more widely available, and what would you do if you were a student?
- Be attentive or sensitive, regardless of whether the student is motivated by the body, the spirit will be focused on the positive aspects of the student's decision making process;
- Be careful with students, any minor misconduct may have an impact on your future career;
- One of the important factors in gaining credibility in student audiences is the use of credible evidence;
- If you have to make any suggestions on the case, do not forget that you should invite only once, "persecution is rape".

From the above, it is possible to say that every person, based on his "I," performs various tasks in different situations, and this is necessary for his life. In any human being, three components of the transitional condition are at different levels and may be misdiagnosed by misconduct. Consequently, there is a deteriorating relationship between the two parties. Increased or reduced pressure on one of the three components of the transformation causes various difficulties in the communication process. As a result, a person experiences

internal tension. From a transitional analysis perspective, all "I" states should be normally proportionate to the individual's objective.

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